

Dyes as Corrosion Inhibitors for Aluminium Alloys in Acid Media Part-3. Triphenylmethane Dyes as Inhibitors for Aluminium-Copper Alloy in Sulphuric Acid

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The corrosion of Al-4% Cu alloy in sulphuric acid increases with acid concentration and immersion period, the plots of ζ (weight loss) vs C (concn) being parabolic in nature following the equation, $C = k\zeta^n$, where $n = 4.4$ and $k = 6.6 \times 10^{-5}$. At constant acid concentration, the inhibitive efficiency of the triphenylmethane dyes increases with inhibitor concentration whereas at constant inhibitor concentration the efficiency first decreases with the increase in acid concentration upto 1.0 M and then increases; the increase in efficiency in 4 M acid being in the order, methyl violet < fuchsine base < victoria blue < fuchsine acid < light green < crystal violet < malachite green < fast green. The B26S aluminium alloy in 0.25 M H_2SO_4 develops a corrosion potential of -755 mV vs SCE and the potential remains unaffected on addition of inhibitors. Galvanostatic polarisation curves show polarisation of both, the cathodes as well as the anodes. The inhibitors appear to function through general adsorption following Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

SOLUTIONS of sulphuric acid (8–35% by weight) are used for anodising aluminium, while dyes are used to give multicoloured effects to the anodised metal^{1,2}. For electropolishing of aluminium, 20–70% (vol %) sulphuric acid containing 75–15% phosphoric acid is employed³. Although the corrosion of aluminium in acid media and its inhibition has been studied by a number of workers, data regarding the inhibition of corrosion of aluminium in sulphuric acid are not adequate^{4–6}. The present communication, in continuation to the earlier ones^{9,10}, reports the use of some triphenylmethane (TPM) dyes in inhibiting the corrosion of B26S aluminium alloy in sulphuric acid.

Experimental

Rectangular specimens of B26S aluminium (Indian Aluminium Co. Ltd.) were used for the determination of the corrosion rates. The composition of the alloy was found¹¹ to be: Cu, 3.88; Mn, 0.87; Si, 0.59; Fe, 0.43; Mg, $\leq 0.32\%$; Al remainder. The specimens (50×40×0.9 mm) were polished and the weight-loss data collected according to the method described earlier^{12,13}. The test specimens were exposed to sulphuric acid solutions in the concentration range 0.005–4.0 M containing upto 0.5% of TPM dyes.

For galvanostatic polarisation studies, circular metal coupons (dia. 28.4 mm with a handle 32.2×4.8 mm) were used. The area exposed to the test solution was 6.33 cm² while the polarising current density was varied in the range 1.58×10^{-5} to 3.95×10^{-5} A cm⁻². The potentials were recorded

with an accuracy of ± 5 mV by a Philips D.C. microvoltmeter.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Figs. 1–8 and Tables 1 and 2. Inhibitor efficiency, expressed as percent inhibition (P.I.) is defined as

$$P.I. = \frac{W_u - W_i}{W_u} \times 100$$

where W_i is weight loss (mg) of metal in inhibited acid and W_u is weight loss (mg) in uninhibited solution.

Corrosion of B26S aluminium in plain sulphuric acid:

Effect of acid concentration and exposure period
The effect of acid concentration and exposure period on the weight-loss of B26S aluminium in sulphuric acid is shown in Figs. 1–2. Fig 2 shows that the increase in corrosion with time is greater the higher the acid concentration, as is evident from an increase in the slope of the linear portion of the plots. The slightly lower corrosion for 12 h immersion period may be due to the induction period required to start the corrosion reaction after dissolving the oxide film from the metal surface¹⁴. A similar behaviour has also been observed for aluminium in hydrochloric acid by Elawady and Ahmed¹⁵.

Variation of pH, specific conductivity and relative corrosivity with acid concentration: The variation of the solution pH, specific conductivity and relative

Fig. 1. Effect of acid concn. on corrosion of B26S aluminium in H_2SO_4 .

Fig. 2. Effect of exposure period on corrosion of B26S aluminium in H_2SO_4 .

corrosivity (weight-loss per unit molarity, $mg\ dm^{-2}\ M^{-1}$) with acid concentration is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of acid concn. on pH and specific conductivity of solution, and weight-loss and relative corrosivity of B26S aluminium in H_2SO_4 .

The results show that when pH of the solution decreases, the specific conductivity and the rate of corrosion ($mg/dm^2/day$) increase with the increase in acid concentration. Here also the increase in corrosion as well as the conductivity is not in the same proportion as that in acid concentration. This is evident from the values of relative corrosivity which decreases with the increase in acid concentration. The weight-loss data when plotted against the concentration of acid, give a parabolic curve (Fig. 3). From the data it may be generalised that the extent of corrosion (ζ) varies with acid concentration (C) following the parabolic equation of the type 1^6 ,

$$C = K\zeta^n$$

where ζ is weight loss ($mg\ dm^{-2}$) of the specimen, C is molarity of acid, and n and k are constants with n is 4.4 and k is 6.8×10^{-9} .

Corrosion in presence of inhibitors :

To assess their protective value, TPM dyes like victoria blue, fast green, light green, malachite green, fuchsine acid, fuchsine base, crystal violet and methyl violet 6B were added to solutions of sulphuric acid. The pH values of 0.1% aqueous solutions of inhibitors lie in the range 3.1 (fast green) to 6.8 (light green) and are non-corrosive to aluminium. A 0.25 M H_2SO_4 solution shows a pH of 0.35 while the pH values of inhibited acid (0.25 M H_2SO_4 + 0.1% inhibitor) lie in the range 0.30 (fast green and malachite green) to 0.32, i.e. the inhibitors do not have much effect on pH of the acid.

As many of the results on inhibitor efficiency mentioned in the present work were obtained with experiments in 0.25 M H_2SO_4 , it was considered necessary to determine the mean weight-loss in this concentration of the acid. From 43 replicate measurements the average weight-loss was found to be $20.0 \pm 0.4\ mg$. The standard deviation was calculated to be $0.7234 \approx 0.7\ mg$.

Effect of inhibitor concentration : From Fig. 4 it is evident that the inhibitive efficiency of various dyes in 0.25 M sulphuric acid at 30° increases with inhibitor concentration. The general order of efficiency of the different dyes in the concentration range studied has been found to be, methyl violet 6B < fuchsine base < fuchsine acid < crystal violet < victoria blue < light green < malachite green < fast green.

Effect of acid concentration : Fig. 5 shows that in all the cases, the inhibitive efficiency first decreases with the increase in acid concentration upto 1 M and then increases upto 4 M. At 0.1% inhibitor concentration in 0.25 M H_2SO_4 , the efficiency of different dyes is found to increase in the order, methyl violet 6B (27%) < fuchsine base < fuchsine acid < crystal violet < victoria blue (38%) < light green < malachite green < fast green (66%). In 4 M acid, the order of increase in efficiency is methyl violet 6B (25%) < fuchsine base < victoria blue < fuchsine acid < light green (41%) < crystal

Fig. 4 Effect of inhibitor concn. on inhibitive efficiency of some triphenylmethane dyes for B26S aluminium in 0.25 M H₂SO₄ at 30° for 1 day.

Fig. 5. Effect of concn. of H₂SO₄ on inhibitive efficiency of triphenylmethane dyes for B26S aluminium at 30°.

violet < malachite green < fast green (54%). Even in 8 M acid (results not reported), the same order of efficiency persists but the inhibitive efficiencies are higher than those in 4 M acid [methyl violet 6B (35.5%) - fast green (58.8%)].

Effect of temperature: Fig. 6 shows the effect of temperature on the weight-loss of B26S aluminium in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ containing 0.5% inhibitor at various temperatures. The results show that as the temperature is increased, the extent of corrosion also increases, it being approximately doubled for every 10° rise in temperature. However, from Table 1 it is apparent that the inhibitive efficiency of all the inhibitors increases with a rise in temperature. The

Fig. 6. Influence of temp. on inhibitive efficiency of triphenylmethane dyes for B26S aluminium in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for 10 h.

inhibitors thus belong to a class of compounds which can be considered for providing corrosion inhibition at elevated temperatures. Such substances are supposed to be firmly held on the metal surface either by forces of specific adsorption or chemisorption. In general, in the range 30-60°, the efficiency of the inhibitors increases in the order, crystal violet < fuchsine acid < methyl violet 6B < light green < victoria blue < fuchsine base < fast green < malachite green.

The values of energy of activation (*E*) were calculated from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log \zeta \rightarrow 1/T$ and are given in Table 1. The energy of activation has a value of ~64 kJ mol⁻¹. In inhibited acid also the values are almost the same. The almost similar values of *E* in inhibited as well as uninhibited acid indicate that the behaviour of inhibitors is like that of the stable poisons in heterogeneous catalysis which do not affect the temperature coefficient of the reaction¹⁷. The almost identical values of *E* for all the inhibitors suggest that the inhibitors are similar in their mechanism of action¹⁸ and the order of efficiency may be related to the pre-exponential factor *A* by the equation,

$$\log \zeta = \log A - E/RT \quad (i)$$

This is further related to the concentration, steric effect, metal characteristics, etc.

If it is assumed that the inhibitor is adsorbed on the metal surface in the form of a monomolecular film, covering at any instant a fraction of the total surface in uniform or random manner, then the heat of adsorption of the inhibitor can be calculated from the equation,

$$Q = 2.303 \times R \log \frac{\theta_2}{1-\theta_2} - \log \frac{\theta_1}{1-\theta_1} \left(\frac{T_1 \times T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \right) \quad (ii)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 are the fractions of the metal surface covered by the inhibitor ($(W_u - W_1)/W_1$) at temperatures *T*₁ and *T*₂ (K), respectively, and *Q* is the heat of adsorption. From Table 1 it is evident

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON INHIBITIVE EFFICIENCY, ENERGY OF ACTIVATION (E), HEAT OF ADSORPTION (Q) AND FREE ENERGY OF ADSORPTION (ΔG_A) FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.5 M H_2SO_4 CONTAINING TPM DYES

 Specimen size = 5×4 cm, Inhibitor concn. = 0.5%, Exposure period = 10 h

Inhibitor	P.I. at				E kJ mol ⁻¹	Q (kJ mol ⁻¹) for the range			Mean ΔG_A kJ mol ⁻¹
	30°	40°	50°	60°		30–40°	40–50°	50–60°	
Nil	(8.1)*	(20.3)	(43.6)	(88.7)	63.6	—	—	—	—
Victoria blue	19.8	32.5	37.2	39.5	58.1	12.7	4.1	2.1	-10.5
Fast green	49.4	56.6	58.5	61.9	61.1	5.5	1.5	3.1	-13.0
Light green	24.7	31.5	35.1	36.1	62.3	6.4	3.2	0.9	-10.5
Malachite green	50.6	59.6	64.9	67.3	54.6	6.9	4.2	2.8	-13.8
Fuchsine base	22.2	37.9	42.2	43.5	59.4	14.3	3.6	1.2	-10.9
Fuchsine acid	7.4	15.9	18.3	19.1	62.3	16.0	3.7	0.9	-7.9
Crystal violet	3.7	8.8	9.4	12.1	61.9	17.5	1.3	5.9	-6.3
Methyl-violet 6B	20.9	30.0	33.5	34.4	61.9	9.0	3.2	0.8	-10.9

 *The values in parentheses indicate weight-loss (mg) in plain 0.5 M H_2SO_4 .

TABLE 2—TAFEL PARAMETERS AND INHIBITOR EFFICIENCIES OF TRIPHENYLMETHANE DYES FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.25 M H_2SO_4

 Surface area of specimen = 6.33 cm², Inhibitor concn. = 0.002 M, Temp. = 30 ± 0.5°

Inhibitor	Open circuit potential mV (vs SOE)	Tafel slope mV/decade		Corrosion current (A cm ⁻² , × 10 ⁴), from extra- plotation of		Inhibitor efficiency (%) calculated from		Weight-loss data
		Cathodic	Anodic	Cathodic Tafel line	Anodic Tafel line	Extrapolation of		
						Cathodic Tafel line	Anodic Tafel line	
Nil	-755	133	450	3.98	3.47	—	—	—
Victoria blue	-755	95	230	2.4	2.4	39.7	30.8	39.0
Fast green	-755	102	190	1.66	1.7	58.3	51.0	63.0
Light green	-745	87	140	2.24	2.0	43.7	42.4	48.5
Malachite green	-745	137	220	1.62	1.32	59.3	47.5	56.5
Fuchsine base	-745	102	190	2.63	2.4	33.9	30.8	26.5
Fuchsine acid	-745	97	270	2.7	2.5	32.2	27.9	36.0
Crystal violet	-750	94	160	2.51	2.04	36.9	41.2	36.5
Methyl violet 6B	-750	57	200	2.88	2.51	27.6	27.6	25.5

that in almost all the cases the Q values decrease for higher ranges of temperatures.

The values of free energy of adsorption from aqueous solution (ΔG_A) were calculated with the help of the equation¹⁹,

$$\log C = \log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} - \log B \quad (\text{iii})$$

where, $\log B = -1.74 - (\Delta G_A / 2.303 RT)$

The values of ΔG_A (Table 1) show that malachite green and fast green which are the most efficient inhibitors of all the compounds studied exhibit more negative free energies of adsorption. This suggests that they are strongly adsorbed on the metal surface. Crystal violet which is the least efficient inhibitor shows a less negative free energy of adsorption.

Polarisation behaviour : B26S aluminium when immersed in 0.25 M H_2SO_4 developed a steady state potential of -755 mV vs SCE. In the presence of various dyes also the corrosion potentials were found to be almost the same (within ±10 mV, Table 2). This suggests that the inhibitors have no preferential action on local anodes or cathodes.

Anodic and cathodic galvanostatic polarisation curves for B26S aluminium in 0.25 M H_2SO_4 alone and containing 0.002 M concentration of the various inhibitors are shown in Fig. 7. The curves show polarisation of both, the anodes as well as the cathodes.

Mechanism of inhibition : The TPM dyes are considered to be cationic compounds²⁰ having the general structure²¹,

where, X = H, NH_2 , $NHCH_3$, $N(CH_3)_2$, $N(CH_3)_3$, C_6H_5 , and, R = H, CH_3 , C_2H_5 , C_6H_5 .

In addition, fuchsine acid and fuchsine base contain some other substituent groups while victoria blue contains a naphthalene ring instead of a benzene one. In strong acid media, the ionisation of the molecules will be suppressed and the cationic

Fig. 7. Effect of current density on cathode and anode potentials of B26S aluminium in 0.25 M H₂SO₄ containing 0.002 M inhibitor.

form will not be more predominant. This will result in the inhibitor molecule functioning as a single entity and getting adsorbed through the polar units like nitrogen, chlorine etc. Such adsorption may lead to diminution of attack, and the efficiency will depend on the orientation of the molecule.

The corrosion potentials of B26S aluminium in inhibited acid are almost the same (within ± 10 mV) as that in plain 0.25 M H₂SO₄ and thus indicate general adsorption of the inhibitors. The anodic

and cathodic galvanostatic polarisation curves for aluminium in inhibited acid also show the polarisation of both, the local anodes as well as the cathodes. Further, when $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ is plotted against $\log C$ straight lines are obtained in the case of fast green, light green, victoria blue, fuchsine acid and methyl violet 6B (Fig. 8). In case of malachite green, crystal violet and fuchsine base, straight lines are obtained at higher range of concentrations (0.05–0.5%). Thus the data suggest that the inhibitors cover both the anodic and cathodic regions through general adsorption following Langmuir isotherm.

Fig. 8. Langmuir adsorption isotherms for corrosion of B26S aluminium in 0.2 M H₂SO₄ containing various inhibitors.

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